

table). Plants treated with neem seed kernel extract, Nochi, white babul, *polyalthia*, and carbendazim yielded more than the control (see table). ■

Efficacy of *Ipomoea cornea* in controlling rice sheath rot

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We studied the efficacy of plant products and chemicals to control rice sheath rot caused by *Sarocladium oryzae*.

Field trials were conducted during 1993 dry (kharif) season. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with 10 treatments (see table) and three replications. The 25-d-old seedlings of cultivar ADT36 were planted at 15- × 10-cm spacing in 5- × 2-m plots. One trial was performed under artificial inoculation conditions and the other under natural infection conditions. The trials were

simultaneously conducted in adjacent fields.

In the artificial inoculation trial, the syringe inoculation method was used because of its greater efficacy when compared with other methods. In each plot, 200 unemerged panicles were syringe-inoculated with 0.2 ml of spore suspension that contained 104 conidia ml⁻¹.

The first spraying was carried out 24 h after inoculation. The second spraying was done 15 d later. The plant products used were *Ipomoea cornea* leaf extract (10%), *Prosopis julifera* leaf extract (10%), neem seed kernel extract (5%), and neem oil (3%).

In the natural infection trial, no inoculation was done.

Fifteen days before harvest, 100 inoculated panicles from the artificial inoculation trial and 100 panicles from the natural infection trial were randomly selected to assess sheath rot incidence. *I. cornea* extract, *P. julifera* extract, and Bavistin were highly effective, recording sheath rot incidence of 11.0, 16.3, and 11.7%, respectively, compared with 72.7% in the control under artificial inoculation conditions (see table). The same trend also occurred under natural infection conditions. ■

Efficacy of plant products and chemicals in controlling rice sheath rot.^a

Treatment	Artificially inoculated plants		Naturally infected plants	
	Sheath rot ^a incidence (%)	Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	Sheath rot incidence (%)	Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)
Neem seed kernel extract, 5%	18.3	733	8.3	1208
Neem oil, 3%	20.0	910	5.7	1158
Bavistin, 0.1% + copper oxychloride, 0.25%	17.3	608	7.3	1225
<i>Prosopis julifera</i> leaf extract, 10%	16.3	892	5.3	1033
<i>Ipomoea cornea</i> leaf extract, 10%	11.0	879	4.3	1067
Bavistin, 0.1%	11.7	642	6.7	1121
Dithane M45, 0.2%	18.3	808	9.3	998
Ziram, 0.3%	15.7	692	7.3	708
Copper oxychloride, 0.25%	22.0	992	8.0	1158
Control	72.7	542	38.7	700
CD (P=0.05)	13.2	ns ^b	6.62	ns

^aMean of 3 replications. ^bns = not significant.

Integrated pest management—insects

Effect of steam distillate extracts of rice cultivars on rice thrips

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We tested the reaction of 122 rice accessions against rice thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall) under field and screen-house conditions at the Annamalai University experimental farm during July 1993 and 1994. We used a 0-9 scale (Heinrichs et al 1985) to score the reactions.

Steam distillates of six cultivars—highly resistant Ptb33 and IR62, resistant IET12008, susceptible ADT40, and highly susceptible IR64 and Rasi—showing similar reactions under both field and

screenhouse conditions were prepared (Saxena and Okech, 1985) and bioassayed to assess the nymphal mortality of *S. biformis* and effect on fecundity of adults.

Using a hand atomizer, the extracts (see table) were sprayed on individual 21-d-old TN1 seedlings. One ml of suspension containing 2000 ppm of the active ingredient was delivered. Each treatment was replicated five times. Controls with acetone and water sprays were maintained.

Each potted seedling was put into a mylar film cage (45 cm tall × 10 cm diameter) and infested with a pair of freshly enclosed adult thrips. The eggs laid female⁻¹ were counted 3 d after release.

In another experiment with a similar set of treatments (see table), 21-d-old TN1 seedlings were sprayed with 1 ml of extract

Laboratory evaluation of steam distillate extracts of certain rice accessions against *S. biformis*.^a

Treatment (2000 ppm)	Total eggs laid ^b (no.)	Larval mortality ^c (%)
Ptb33	10.8 d ± 0.4	70.0 a ± 4.7
IR62	13.2 c ± 0.6	60.0 a ± 4.7
IET12008	13.2 c ± 0.6	64.0 a ± 4.7
ADT40	12.8 c ± 0.5	43.3 b ± 2.7
IR64	16.2 b ± 0.6	40.0 b ± 4.7
Rasi	14.2 c ± 0.4	39.6 b ± 2.7
Acetone	20.0 a ± 0.6	6.6 c ± 2.7
Control	20.0 a ± 1.0	3.3 c ± 2.7

^aIn a column, means (± SE) followed by the same letter do not differ significantly by DMRT (p = 0.05). ^bFive replications. ^cThree replications.

of each cultivar at the concentration of 2000 ppm. Plants treated with acetone and water alone served as controls. Each treatment was replicated three times. Treated seedlings were confined individually in test